

OA Diamond & Institutional Publishing Landscape Survey

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

The OA Diamond and Institutional Publishing Landscape Survey has just launched. View the questionnaire in full [here](#).

With the survey, we hope to map how Institutional Publishing is currently organised in order to understand existing challenges and develop resources, tools, policies, and strategies which support the Institutional Publishers and associated stakeholders. The survey will remain open until 30 April.

DIAMAS will create a registry of “institutional publishing service providers” through the landscape mapping conducted in the survey, building a community ready to share knowledge and collaborate. A series of best practices, policy recommendations, and guidelines will be created to help strengthen the community and set evidence-based quality standards.

Questions are aimed at Institutional Publishing Services Providers (IPSPs) from the European Research Area. To read more about Institutional Publishers – [read our recent blog](#).

We are also hosting a series of SURVEY-A-THONS to support respondents. For details about these sessions (times, dates, languages, etc.), see [this page](#).

You can download the survey in PDF to preview all the questions [here](#).

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